

TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF BACTERIAL POLYSACCHARIDES

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Abstract: The aim of this work was to develop a technology for obtaining bacterial exopolysaccharides. The problem was solved by using the bacterial strain *Halomonas* sp. as a polysaccharide producer. The optimal parameters of bacterial cultivation have been determined. A technological scheme for obtaining bacterial polysaccharides has been developed, which includes such stages as the cultivation of bacteria, the separation of bacterial biomass from the culture liquid, desalting, precipitation, washing and drying. The results obtained show that bacteria have a high potential for the yield of bacterial exopolysaccharides (3,73 g/L).

Keywords: bacterial polysaccharides, *Halomonas* sp., food biopolymers, isolation of polysaccharides

Introduction

Despite the diversity of biopolymers and their practical significance, only a few have been industrially implemented [1-3]. In the global hydrocolloid market, polysaccharides from algae and plants, such as alginate, starch, pectin, carrageenan, galactomannan, etc., dominate, while the share of bacterial exopolysaccharides (BEPS) does not exceed 10% [4-6]. This is largely due to the low yield and high cost of the resulting products. Innovative approaches are required to replace plant hydrocolloids with microbial analogs [7-11].

The inhibiting factors of their industrial production include the imperfection of production technology, resulting in high production costs. Additionally, significant attention is needed for the development of an efficient technological line for fermentation and polymer extraction from the nutrient medium [12]. Their wide range of applications is due to their diverse and modifiable properties as thickeners, gelling agents, film-forming agents, stabilizers, texturizers, and emulsifiers. Moreover, research in recent years has shown that some microbial polysaccharides possess significant immunomodulatory properties (anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial) or hypocholesterolemic and hypoglycemic properties, making them ideal candidates for use in "functional food products" or "nutraceuticals" [13].

Halophilic soil microorganisms constitute a group of microorganisms that can grow in environments with high salt concentrations [14]. Most halophiles are found in hypersaline waters, soils,

salt, and saline deposits [15]. Aerobic, anaerobic, and facultative microorganisms of archaea and bacteria from saline waters of the Dead Sea, the Mediterranean Sea, the Great Salt Lake (Utah, USA), Antarctic lakes, Magadi, and other regions have been studied and categorized into groups according to their growth and development in a saline environment [16]. The salt concentration for weak halophiles is 2-5%, 5-20% for moderate halophiles, and 20-30% for strong halophiles [15-17]. These bacteria continue their activity through proton transfer systems in the cytoplasmic membrane (ATP and sodium replacement by a proton pump) [18-19].

The aim of this study was to develop a technology for obtaining polysaccharides from *Halomonas* sp. This task is solved by using the strain of bacteria *Halomonas* sp. as a polysaccharide producer. The mentioned strain is deposited in the Collection of Microorganisms of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Research Methods

The research focused on the bacteria *Halomonas* sp., isolated in 2019 from hypersaline water bodies in the Republic of Karakalpakstan: a lake near Kungurad [20]. Water samples were collected from the bottom of the drying lake (depth 10-20 cm) in May 2019 and placed in sterile plastic containers. The salinity of the samples was determined using a MASTER-S28a refractometer (ATOGO, Japan). For the cultivation of halophilic bacteria, a liquid medium of the following composition (g/L) was used: NaCl – 156.0; MgCl₂·6H₂O – 13.0; MgSO₄·7H₂O – 20.0; CaCl₂·6H₂O – 1.0; KCl – 4.0; NaHCO₃ – 0.2; NaBr – 0.5; glucose – 10.0; yeast extract – 10.0 (pH 7.2).

Bacterial cultivation in a batch process was carried out in a thermostat (Memmert, Germany) in 1-liter Erlenmeyer flasks containing 500 ml of nutrient medium with air bubbling (aeration, 100%) and illumination with white light with a periodicity of 14 hours of light and 10 hours of dark phase at 35-37°C, with a ratio of nutrient medium to inoculum (titer 10⁸ cells per 1 ml) of 100:1 [21].

For the isolated bacterial culture, colony morphology was described, Gram staining was performed according to the procedure [22], tests with potassium hydroxide were conducted, and sporulation was stained according to [23]. Examination was carried out on a laboratory microscope DM1000 (Leica, Germany) to determine motility, cell shape, and size at different growth stages in liquid and solid nutrient media [23, 24]. To classify halophilic microorganisms into one of four groups, isolates were tested for their ability to grow on solid media with different NaCl contents (0.5, 10, 15, and 25%) [25].

From the liquid culture in the stationary growth phase, cells were precipitated by centrifugation (PC-6, Russia) at 4400 rpm for 20 minutes, the supernatant was dialyzed for 24 hours against distilled water through a membrane with an exclusion limit of 12-14 kDa (Scienova GmbH, Germany). Polysaccharides from the dialysate of the culture medium were precipitated with 1.5 volumes of chilled 96% ethanol (4°C, 12 hours), the precipitate (polysaccharides) was separated, washed twice with 200 ml of ethanol (96%), and dried at 25°C. The amount of carbohydrates was determined by the method [26].

Results and Discussion

Samples of hypersaline water and salt crystals were inoculated into nutrient medium with NaCl concentrations ranging from 5 to 30%. Various samples were selected based on the shape, pink-red color of the bacteria, and the formation of individual colonies in nutrient media.

The growth of isolated bacterial colonies in nutrient medium with high salt concentration (20–25%) indicates that the isolated bacteria are halophilic (Fig. 1).

The optimal temperature for bacterial cultivation was determined by growing bacteria in media at temperatures ranging from 15 to 45°C (Fig. 2). The optimal temperature for bacterial cultivation is 35°C.

The pH of the medium is also an important parameter as it indicates the acidity level of the metabolite medium and is a criterion affecting the yield of polysaccharides in the culture medium (Fig. 3). The optimal pH for bacterial cultivation was determined using a pH meter (Mettler-Toledo, China), growing bacteria on solid nutrient media with initial pH values ranging from 5.1 to 9.0. The optimal pH for bacteria was 7.5.

Figure 1. Dependence of cell titer on the salinity of the nutrient medium.

Figure 2. Dependence of EPS yield on medium temperature.

Figure 3. Dependence of cell titer on medium pH.

The nature of the carbon source is an important factor in providing cells with the necessary energy for growth and key metabolites for EPS biosynthesis [27]. Additionally, the composition and structure of the EPS produced by them can vary significantly depending on the type of monosaccharides in the nutrient medium. In this study, the carbon source was chosen based on the cost-effectiveness of EPS production.

The influence of various sugars, including glucose, sucrose, lactose, and fructose, on the growth and EPS production of *Halomonas sp.* was evaluated using liquid nutrient medium HM 20%. The obtained results showed that (Fig. 4) the EPS yield of the culture on media composed of glucose and a mixture of glucose and sucrose was higher than that of other sugars. Sucrose is closest to the highest EPS yield.

Figure 4. Influence of carbon source on growth and EPS production.

The obtained results are consistent with literature data showing that sucrose has the maximum yield as a carbon source and can be used for large-scale EPS production [28].

Several studies on EPS production by microorganisms show that EPS synthesis increases with an increase in carbohydrate abundance in the surrounding environment, and conversely, a decrease in carbohydrate concentration reduces their productivity [29]. However, in some cases, the optimal substrate concentration varies depending on individual strains of microorganisms [30]. It has been established that the maximum EPS yield is 1% (4.31 g/L) at the optimal concentration of the carbon source chosen in previous studies (Fig. 5). I. Llamas et al. reported that halophilic bacteria produce maximum biomass and EPS formation when cultivated in a medium with 1% glucose, while higher concentrations of glucose inhibit both bacterial growth and EPS formation. In the absence of glucose in the medium, the growth of halophilic bacteria was not limited at all, and EPS formation was observed [31].

Figure 5. Influence of carbon source concentration on EPS formation.

It should be noted that in many studies optimizing the cultivation conditions of microorganisms, the maximum biomass content does not correspond to the maximum EPS production. For example, halophilic bacteria show high EPS formation efficiency at low carbon source concentrations in the medium. The concentrations of carbon sources used in the experiments correspond to literature data [32]. The discrepancy between EPS production and biomass accumulation may indicate a stressful state of EPS-producing bacteria, and their biosynthesis may be a factor in adaptation to osmotic stress. In further studies, it was not used as it negatively affected the color and quality of EPS obtained when grown on molasses medium.

Figure 6. Influence of nitrogen source on the growth of halophilic bacteria and EPS formation.

To determine the effect of various nitrogen sources on EPS formation, in addition to the carbon source (1% glucose), organic (peptone, yeast extract) and inorganic (ammonium chloride, sodium nitrate) nitrogen sources were added to the solution at a concentration of 0.5%. According to the results presented, it was noted that the culture of *Halomonas sp.* grows well and produces maximum EPS (3.73 g/L) in a nutrient medium with yeast extract. Thus, in further studies, yeast extract was used as the optimal source of organic nitrogen.

It was found that biomass accumulation increases with increasing concentration of yeast extract in the medium, but EPS biosynthesis decreases. Literature sources indicate that the strain *Rhizobium meliloti* produces maximum EPS with a minimal nitrogen source in the medium [33].

The next stage of the research was to determine the effect of aeration on the growth of *Halomonas sp.* and EPS production by these bacteria. For this purpose, bacteria were grown in HM 20% medium in a shaking incubator at frequencies of 100 and 150 rpm, with air bubbling, and in a static state. The maximum EPS productivity was achieved when aerating the halophilic bacterial culture by shaking at a speed of 150 rpm in 20% HM medium (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Influence of aeration level on the growth of *Halomonas sp.* and EPS production.

As seen from the obtained results, biomass accumulation in the medium and EPS formation also depend on the degree of aeration. The highest amount of biomass and EPS formation observed in the cultivation medium experiments was observed in experiments grown using a shaker (150 rpm) and air bubbler. It can be concluded that the production of bacterial polysaccharides on an industrial scale allows for their cultivation in large-scale air-lift bioreactors.

Next, EPS formation over time was studied under the aforementioned optimal conditions for 13 days (Fig. 4). By the 10th day, bacteria enter the stationary phase, and during this period, the release of polysaccharides is observed.

To isolate exopolysaccharides formed in the cultivated medium, 96% ethanol was used. For this purpose, 100 ml of the cultivated liquid was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 20 minutes. The obtained supernatant was placed in a cellulose dialysis bag Zellu Trans Dialysis Tube T4 and dialyzed at 4°C for 24 hours against 2.5 liters of distilled water (the water was changed twice). Then, the dialysate was mixed with chilled ethanol in a ratio of 1.0:1.5 and kept for 6 hours at a temperature of 4°C to form a dense precipitate. The precipitate of exopolysaccharides was separated from the supernatant by filtration and washed twice with ethanol in a ratio of 1:2 for 30 minutes. The obtained polysaccharides were dried at 25°C for 24 hours in a drying oven.

Figure 8. Influence of cultivation duration on growth and EPS production.

The obtained results demonstrate that bacteria exhibit high potential for bacterial exopolysaccharide yield (3.73 g/L) compared to literature-reported results [34].

Based on the obtained results, a technological scheme for bacterial polysaccharide production (Fig. 9) is proposed, which includes the following steps:

Figure 9. Technological scheme for bacterial polysaccharide production:

1 – nutrient medium reactor, 2 – pump, 3 – inoculum fermenter (100 L), 4 – bacteria cultivation fermenter (1 ton), 5 – bacteria cultivation fermenter (3 tons), 6 – separator, 7 – ethanol reservoir, 8 – reactor for polysaccharide precipitation and washing, 9 – column with ion-exchange sorbent.

A nutrient medium of 1000 L volume is transferred to the fermenter (1), sterilized within the fermenter, and cooled to 35°C. Then, a bacterial inoculum of 10 L volume is added to the fermenter, and bacteria are cultivated in fermenters (4-5) for 5 days until the cell titer reaches 10^9 cells/mL.

Bacterial cultivation is carried out under the following conditions: salt concentration as NaCl – 20%, temperature 35°C, pH 7.5. After reaching a bacterial titer of 10^9 cells/mL and an exopolysaccharide quantity in the culture medium of 3.73 g/L, the culture medium is pumped by the pump (2) to the separator (6) to separate biomass from the culture medium. Subsequently, the culture medium is transferred to a bioreactor (8) for polysaccharide precipitation. Ethanol from the reservoir (7) in a volume of 1500 L is introduced into the bioreactor, the mixture is stirred and kept for 2 hours to form a dense precipitate (mass) of polysaccharides. The supernatant water-alcohol mixture is drained off, the precipitate is washed with ethanol (200 L), filtered, dissolved in distilled water, desalinated in the ion-exchange sorbent column (9), and directed for drying.

Conclusion

The obtained results demonstrate that bacteria exhibit a high potential for the production of bacterial polysaccharides (3.73 g/L). Maintaining nutrient concentration and salt levels in the cultivation medium, a temperature of 37°C, as well as 100% air saturation with the nutrient medium during cultivation, creates optimal conditions for bacterial growth. Control of parameters such as glucose concentration (1%) and pH 7.5 allows for increased bacterial titer and enhanced polysaccharide yield.

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